

Orbital and molecular design of new naphthyl-salen type transition metal complexes toward DSSC dyes

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Abstract : Dye sensitized solar cells (DSSC) emerged as a new class of low cost energy conversion devices. In this study, we investigated a class of transition metal complexes [ML(CH₃OH)]; M = Mn(1), Fe(2), Co(3), Ni(4), Cu(5) and Zn(6) and H₂L is naphthyl-salen Schiff base ligand. The COOH group of the complexes leads to better ability for adsorption of dyes. These complexes were characterized employing elemental analysis, powder X-ray analysis, IR, UV-Vis-NIR electronic spectroscopy and so on. Light absorption of the all the complexes shows that π -conjugated naphthyl ring makes these complexes efficient as dyes in DSSC. However, spatial distribution of excited orbitals associated with absorption properties (UV-Vis absorption spectra) calculated by TD-DFT method revealed one of the important factors about orbitals and molecular design of metal complexes for DSSC dyes.

Keywords : Schiff base complexes, orbital design, TD-DFT calculation, UV-Vis spectra, dye sensitized solar cell (DSSC).

Introduction

In the year 1991, Grätzel and O'Regan firstly reported on a low cost organic material type solar cell, namely dye sensitized solar cells (DSSC) based on TiO₂ materials. Thus, DSSC is one of the organic type solar cells, producing electrical energy by light harvesting of dye molecules. An electron is excited by the photoexcitation of the dye and transferred to conduction band of TiO₂ which transfers to positive electrode and finally returns to ground state dye molecule via oxidation-reduction reaction of electrolyte. At present, DSSC are the most extensively investigated area owing to their applications as low cost photovoltaic devices especially suited for building and automobiles integrated PV and portable or indoor light harvesting applications. Many researches have been performed on DSSC using different type of dyes^{1a}.

For example, Ru²⁺ polypyridyl complexes, [Ru(dcbpyH₂)₂(NCS)₂], [Ru(4,4'-dicarboxy-2,2'-bipyridine)₂(NCS)₂] (commonly called "N3")^{1b} had been widely used as dye component and shows higher conversion efficiency because of long excitation lifetime; however, the metal is rare and expensive²⁻⁷.

In addition, reports on transition metal complexes have demonstrated that organic ligands play important role in enhancing the luminescent color and intensity. Especially, narrowing HOMO-LUMO gap makes expansion of absorption band toward NIR region⁸⁻¹⁰. Although some organic molecules and complexes have been developed as dyes in DSSCs, design and synthesis of organic ligands and their transition metal complexes for application on DSSCs is still a great challenge¹¹⁻¹⁷. In the design of complexes, Schiff base ligands have been widely used as ligands due to their

convenient synthesis.

Herein we have focused on designing of dyes based on salen type Schiff base complexes. We also consider the effect of substituents on the absorption conversion performance theoretically. Our prediction shows that the first row transition metal complexes may be effectively exploited as dyes. In the present article, we present the synthesis and characterization of the new transition metal complexes [ML(CH₃OH)]; M = Mn(**1**), Fe(**2**), Co(**3**), Ni(**4**), Cu(**5**) and Zn(**6**) and H₂L is naphthyl-salen Schiff base ligand and discusses the effect of central metal on absorption characteristic along with computational calculations. The complexes **1-6** were employed to prepare DSSC devices, which could compensate for the absorption of N3 in the high-energy band region of the visible spectrum. Thus, performance of DSSCs based on complexes as sensitizers is investigated in detail.

Experimental

Chemicals and solvents :

All starting materials such as 1-vinyl-naphthalen-2-ol and 2,3-diamino-succinic acid and metal salts M(OAc)₂·xH₂O were obtained from commercial sources. The solvents like methanol and DMF, DMSO were reagent grade and used as supplied.

Instrumentation :

Elemental analyses (C, H, N) were carried out with a Perkin-Elmer 2400II CHNS/O analyzer at the Tokyo University of Science. FT-IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a JASCO FT-IR 4200 plus spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ at 298 K. UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectra and diffuse reflectance electronic spectra were measured on a JASCO V-570 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed on a AIOS/DY2323 with a traditional three electrodes. The working electrode and auxiliary electrode was Pt disc. Ag/AgCl and Pt wire electrode, respectively. Magnetic studies were performed using a Quantum design MPMS-XLSQUID magnetometer. The X-ray diffraction patterns were collected at 298 K on Rigaku Smart lab (CuK α radiation) at the University of Tokyo. Powder crystal structure analysis was carried out with a Rigaku

PDXL2, commercially available program package.

Computational calculations :

All calculation was performed by the Gaussian 09W software Revision A.02 (Gaussian, Inc.)¹⁸. Calculated UV-Vis spectra was gained by TD-DFT with B3LYP functional. Basis sets were Lan12DZ on central metal ion to consider the effect core potential and 6-31(d) on other atoms.

Synthesis :

Naphthyl-salen Schiff base ligand (H₂L) and **5** were synthesized according to the reported method by us¹⁹. To methanol solution of 1 mmol H₂L ligand, 1 mmol M(OAc)₂·xH₂O (M = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn) was added and dissolved. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h, subsequently filtered and collected at room temperature.

1 : Yield 17.9%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 457w, 508w, 565w, 657w, 725w, 753w, 831w, 979w, 1038w, 1097w, 1191w, 1250w, 1293w, 1340w, 1362m, 1385m, 1456w, 1478w, 1542s, 1599s, 1618s (C=N), 1727w, 2950w, 3075w, 3253w; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂MnN₂O₇ : C, 52.96; H, 3.62; N, 4.57. Found : C, 51.95; H, 3.32; N, 4.79%.

2 : Yield 75.0%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 501w, 566w, 618w, 654w, 751w, 831w, 863w, 990w, 1040m, 1028s, 1128s, 1192m, 1212m, 1243m, 1295w, 1342m, 1364m, 1384m, 1423w, 1453w, 1540m, 1579s, 1600s, 1617s (C=N), 1728w, 2962w, 3066w, 3200w; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂FeN₂O₇ : C, 51.96; H, 3.62; N, 4.57. Found : C, 51.87; H, 3.39; N, 4.77%.

3 : Yield 61.4%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 505w, 567w, 659w, 753w, 829w, 977w, 1037w, 1099w, 1188w, 1251w, 1295w, 1340m, 1361m, 1389m, 1435w, 1452w, 1510w, 1541m, 1590s, 1619s (C=N), 1731w, 2954w, 3076w, 3252w; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂CoN₂O₇ : C, 52.28; H, 3.57; N, 4.52. Found : C, 51.98; H, 3.48; N, 4.84%.

4 : Yield 25.0%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 506w, 571w, 655w, 751m, 829w, 982w, 1045w, 1106w, 1199m, 1260w, 1294m, 1364m, 1391m, 1485w, 1542s, 1586s, 1603s, 1618s (C=N), 1721w, 2941w, 3074w; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂NiN₂O₇ : C, 52.32; H, 3.58; N, 4.52. Found : C, 51.98; H, 3.48; N, 4.05%.

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6 : Yield 50.0%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 505w, 575w, 723w, 752w, 835w, 974w, 1032w, 1101w, 1199m, 1282m, 1371m, 1419m, 1483w, 1518w, 1546m, 1575s, 1627s (C=N), 1731w, 2938w, 3062w, 3208w; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{ZnN}_2\text{O}_7$: C, 51.21; H, 3.50; N, 4.42. Found : C, 51.86; H, 3.45; N, 4.78%.

DSSC fabrication :

Negative electrodes were prepared by adding 1.5 g of TiO_2 (P25) to 1.5 g polyethyleneglycol (PEG) and 15% (v/v) of acetic acid. The mixture was stirred for 1 h, resulting in a paste. The paste was extended into 1 cm^2 of Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) glass 2.5 cm^2 by squeegee method. Then the ITO was heated up to 450 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min. Finally, the glass was immersed in dye (**1-4**, **6**) solutions (5×10^{-4} M) for 24 h. Electrolyte was composed of mixture of 0.127 g I_2 , 0.127 g of dimethyl-3-propylimidazolium iodide (DMPImI), 0.134 g of LiI and 0.405 g of tertbutylpyridine (TBP) in 10 mL MeCN. 2–3 drops of the resulting solution were added before measurement.

We prepared three types of positive electrode (ITO glass). One ITO glass was coated with graphite using 10B pencil. Another was ITO glass with rough surface, on which graphite was pasted using 10B pencil. The other ITO glass was exposed to burning candle and covered with graphite. We employed the type 3 positive electrode for measurements (Fig. 1).

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The Schiff base ligand was synthesized employing the condensation reaction of 1-vinyl-naphthalen-2-ol

Scheme 1. Preparation and chemical structures of **1-6**.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the typical DSSC (SLG soda lime glass; ITO indium doped tin oxide).

and 2,3-diamino-succinic acid in the ratio 2 : 1. The reaction of the preformed Schiff base with metal acetate, $\text{M}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Mn}(1), \text{Fe}(2), \text{Co}(3), \text{Ni}(4)$ and $\text{Zn}(6)$) afforded polycrystalline solid compounds (Scheme 1). 2,3-Diamino-succinic acid and $\text{Cu}(5)$ complex was previously synthesized and characterized thoroughly and reported¹⁹. The stoichiometry of the rest of the complexes **1-4** and **6** obtained was established through elemental analysis and FT-IR which was confirmed by structural characterization.

IR spectral studies :

FT-IR spectra of the complexes have provided conclusion for the mode of coordination from the dianionic moiety (nap^{2-}) to the metal ions. The positions of bands are summarized in Experimental section. The spectra of all the complexes contain a band in 1617–1627 cm^{-1} range is the characteristic of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ iminic bond. The spectra also contained bands in 1721–1731 cm^{-1} range, represent the characteristic stretching frequency for free uncoordinated $-\text{COOH}$ of the unionized car-

boxylic functions of ligand. The appearance of medium intensity band in low frequency region characteristic of M–N ($\sim 570\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the bands M–O ($\sim 505\text{ cm}^{-1}$) stretching vibrations were also present in the spectra of the complexes.

X-Ray crystallographic studies :

The results of the X-ray analysis on crystals of the complexes **1-4** and **6** with refinement parameters are

summarized in Table 1. As shown in Fig. 2, the structures of the independent molecules in the unit cells are presented for respective complexes (significant atoms are labeled). The selected bond lengths are summarized in Table 2. The selected bond angles for the complexes (**1-3**) and (**4** and **6**) are compiled in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively. All the complexes are within common range for the related ones²⁰. The metal ions

Fig. 2. Crystal structures of complexes (a) $[\text{MnL}(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})](\mathbf{1})$, (b) $[\text{FeL}(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})](\mathbf{2})$, (c) $[\text{CoL}(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})](\mathbf{3})$, (d) $[\text{NiL}(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})](\mathbf{4})$, (e) $[\text{CuL}(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})](\mathbf{5})$ and (f) $[\text{ZnL}(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})](\mathbf{6})$.

Table 1. Crystal data and structural refinement for **1-4** and **6**

	1	2	3	4	6
CCDC	1540630	1540629	1540628	1540631	1540627
Empirical formula	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ MnN ₂ O ₇	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ FeN ₂ O ₇	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ CoN ₂ O ₇	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ NiN ₂ O ₇	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ ZnN ₂ O ₇
Formula weight	541.41	542.32	513.37	545.17	551.89
Crystal system	Triclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Triclinic	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1	<i>P</i> 2	<i>P</i> 2	<i>P</i> -1	<i>P</i> -1
<i>a</i> (Å)	11.21(12)	14.10(2)	10.779(7)	9.39(8)	12.568(19)
<i>b</i> (Å)	15.47(6)	12.87(2)	16.177(4)	16.06(3)	17.41(2)
<i>c</i> (Å)	9.63(11)	110.11(2)	7.740(11)	7.977(9)	10.893(18)
α (°)	92.46(11)			95.43(15)	109.83(18)
β (°)	111.79(10)	106.02(2)	99.04(18)	107.62(7)	102.46(11)
γ (°)	93.28(15)			99.48(7)	71.10(10)
V (Å ³)	1550(3)	1921.1(6)	1332.8(6)	1118(2)	2096(6)
Z	2	2	2	2	2
Rwp (%)	2.86	3.97	1.92	5.66	3.90

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) for **1-4** and **6**

	1	2	3	4	6				
Mn–O1	1.933(2)	Fe–O1	1.9499(3)	Co–O1	1.8961(5)	Ni–O1	1.878(4)	Zn–O1	2.312(3)
Mn–O2	1.987(2)	Fe–O2	1.9607(5)	Co–O2	1.8924(6)	Ni–O2	2.064(3)	Zn–O2	1.879(3)
Mn–O3	2.087(2)	Fe–O3	2.1021(4)	Co–O3	2.1240(3)	Ni–O3	1.850(15)	Zn–O3	2.125(4)
Mn–N1	2.144(3)	Fe–N1	2.1312(6)	Co–N1	1.9104(7)	Ni–N1	1.944(3)	Zn–N1	2.321(3)
Mn–N2	2.130(14)	Fe–N2	2.1490(3)	Co–N2	1.9305(5)	Ni–N2	2.142(3)	Zn–N2	2.268(3)

Table 3. Selected bond angles (°) for **1-3**

	1	2	3		
O1–Mn–O3	101.76(8)	O1–Fe–O3	102.533(4)	O1–Co–O3	92.085(17)
O2–Mn–O3	97.76(10)	O2–Fe–O3	96.518(16)	O2–Co–O3	93.355(8)
O1–Mn–O2	97.76(10)	O1–Fe–O2	108.420(4)	O1–Co–O2	89.902(7)
O1–Mn–N1	80.99(17)	O1–Fe–N1	83.554(5)	O1–Co–N1	91.488(7)
O1–Mn–N2	147.30(6)	O1–Fe–N2	147.158(9)	O1–Co–N2	164.861(4)
O2–Mn–N1	162.23(2)	O2–Fe–N1	161.950(5)	O2–Co–N1	173.835(2)
O2–Mn–N2	83.73(10)	O2–Fe–N2	84.626(9)	O2–Co–N2	91.471(5)
O3–Mn–N1	92.54(11)	O3–Fe–N1	93.845(16)	O3–Co–N1	92.596(7)
O3–Mn–N2	106.23(8)	O3–Fe–N2	105.795(5)	O3–Co–N2	102.880(16)
N1–Mn–N2	79.49(11)	N1–Fe–N2	78.341(6)	N1–Co–N2	85.632(5)

occupy the inner chamber of the Schiff base ligand and exhibits penta-coordinated geometry whereby the dianionic (nap)²⁻ binds in tetradentate fashion via two oxygen (O1 and O2) and two nitrogen (N1 and N2) of the Schiff base ligand which are approximately coplanar. The tetragonality index, $\tau = (\beta - \alpha)/60$, where α and β are given by opposing angles in the coordination polyhedron. The values of τ are zero and unity, for perfect square pyramidal and trigonal bipyramidal

respectively. The values of τ for complexes are found to be 0.248(**1**), 0.246(**2**), 0.149(**3**), 0.184(**4**) and 0.164(**6**). According to these values, the coordination geometry around the metal ions is best described as distorted square-based pyramidal with one methanol at axial position.

Magnetic properties :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements for powder

Table 4. Selected bond angles ($^{\circ}$) for **4** and **6**.

4		6	
O1–Ni–O3	101.23(9)	O1–Zn–O3	114.57(13)
O2–Ni–O3	99.35(8)	O2–Zn–O3	100.29(13)
O1–Ni–O2	95.50(11)	O1–Zn–O2	85.10(15)
O1–Ni–N1	87.98(11)	O1–Zn–N1	76.51(12)
O1–Ni–N2	156.43(5)	O1–Zn–N2	152.17(3)
O2–Ni–N1	167.51(2)	O2–Zn–N1	94.57(12)
O2–Ni–N2	87.88(12)	O2–Zn–N2	108.86(11)
O3–Ni–N1	91.70(8)	O3–Zn–N1	162.034(13)
O3–Ni–N2	101.21(9)	O3–Zn–N2	87.21(16)

samples (**1-4**) were carried out by the SQUID based magnetometer in the temperature 5–300 K. The magnetic susceptibilities are shown as a function of temperature in Fig. 3. The magnetic data were fitted by employing Curie-Weiss law, $\chi = C/(T+\theta)$. Magnetic moments were obtained from the relation $\mu = 2.828(\chi T)^{1/2}$ (B.M.). The number of unpaired electrons (n) was predicted from μ by the relation $\mu = \{n(n+2)\}^{1/2}$.²¹ The observed effective magnetic moment along with number of unpaired electrons are

shown in Table 5. The n values are in agreement with expected d-electron configurations of the coordination geometries determined.

Table 5. Effective moment (μ) for the paramagnetic complexes (**1-4**)

Complexes	μ (B.M.)	No. of unpaired electrons
1	6.03	5
2	4.64	4
3	4.05	3
4	2.91	2

UV-Vis-NIR electronic spectra and TD-DFT calculations :

The electronic spectra of the 3×10^{-5} M DMF solutions of the complexes are shown in Fig. 4(a). The intense high energy absorption bands appear at ~ 270 nm (Band 1) and a weak band at ~ 400 nm (Band 2) in all complexes are due to $\pi-\pi^*$. The complex **4** shows highest absorption coefficient whereas in complex **6**, band 2 is broad and prominent as compared to other

Fig. 3. The χ_m vs T and $\chi_m T$ vs T plots for complexes **1-4**; Inset : The χ^{-1} vs T plots.

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complexes. From these observations, it may be concluded that structure of the ligand affects the absorption bands. Comparing with the absorption spectra of Ru²⁺ polypyridyl complexes, [Ru(dcbpyH₂)₂(NCS)₂], N3, apparently all the complexes could better compensate for the absorption of N3 in the low wavelength region of the visible spectrum²². Therefore, we apply complexes (1-6) as dyes to apply in the DSSC devices. The high molar extinction coefficient indicates that they possess a better light-harvesting ability in this low wavelength region compared with N3. Meanwhile the ligand has carboxylic groups, which could adsorb on the TiO₂ surface.

The solid state adsorption spectra were also obtained to gain insight for the d-d transitions in the complexes 1-6 shown in Fig. 4(b). It has been found that absorption band at ~700 nm appears in all complexes is due to d-d transitions.

The electronic transition in UV spectra of complexes 1-6 have been carried out employing TD-DFT (B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p)) method and provided in Fig. 5. The molecular orbitals (MOs) HOMO and LUMO were provided in Fig. 6. To support the DFT geometry optimizations, the calculated geometries were compared with the experimental spectra data. A comparison of the theoretical data for the complexes allows us

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. (a) Electronic absorption spectra for 1-6 (3×10^{-5} M DMF). (b) Solid state diffuse reflectance spectra for 1-6.

Fig. 5. Calculated UV-Vis-NIR spectra.

Fig. 6. Orbital distribution (around HOMO or LUMO) before and after intraligand transitions for 1-6, transition energies (in wavelengths) are 329.0, 322.6, 325.3, 361.4, 327.3, and 323.7 nm, respectively.

to assess the extent of spectra and to correctly describe the electronic spectra.

The broadening of the peak in Fig. 5 is generated by two peaks in the absorption spectra at ~ 300 nm and 400 nm. Band 1 and 2 arise due to $(\pi-\pi^*)$ charge

transfer of the naphthyl ring. It is clear from Fig. 5 that these two bands are comparable, but complex 6 show the broadest absorption band among all molecules.

It may also be concluded from Fig. 6 that the complex 4 shows longest wavelength. It is plausible to

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Table 6. Summary of electrochemical parameters of the complexes **1-6**

Complexes	E_p^a (V vs Ag/AgCl)	E_p^c (V vs Ag/AgCl)	E_p^a (V vs NHE)	E_p^c (V vs NHE)	HOMO (eV)	LUMO (eV)
1	-1.170	0.307	-0.970	0.507	-4.95	-3.47
2	-1.150	0.476	-0.950	0.676	-5.12	-3.49
3	-1.170	0.103	-0.970	0.303	-4.74	-3.47
4	-1.120	0.187	-0.920	0.387	-4.83	-3.52
5	-1.300	0.313	-1.100	0.513	-4.95	-3.34
6	-1.130	0.545	-0.93	0.745	-5.19	-3.51

conclude that visual appearance of electron transition by band 2 that causes power generation are shown in Fig. 6. It may also be concluded that it is only the complexes **4** that can be used as dye as this follow the trend for DSSC power generation effective. In contrast to **4**, other complexes are not suitable for this purpose due to unsuitable orbital distribution of excited states (far from -COOH groups).

cyclic voltammograms (CV), these sensitizers have low lying highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) levels from -4.74 to -5.19 eV. All HOMO are lower than the redox potential of I^-/I_3^- (-4.85 eV vs vacuum), indicating the favorable regeneration. The lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) energy of the complexes are -3.47(**1**), -3.49(**2**), -3.47(**3**), -3.52(**4**), -3.34(**5**) and -3.51(**6**) eV, respectively. All calculated

Scheme 2. Schematic orbital energy levels of (a) TiO_2 and I_2 and (b) comparison with complexes (**1-6**) used as dyes in DSSCs (upper lines are HOMO and lower line are LUMO of the complexes).

Electrochemical properties :

We investigated the UV-Vis absorption spectra of complexes **1-6**. The HOMO-LUMO energy levels are crucial in selecting sensitizers for DSSCs, which were determined by cyclic voltammetry in a 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP). The electrochemical parameters are compiled in Table 6. As estimated from the onset oxidation potentials in the

LUMOs are higher than the conduction band of TiO_2 (-4.40 eV vs vacuum), leading to effective electron transfer (Scheme 2).

Characterization parameters for DSSC :

The solar to electricity conversion efficiency (η) of the solar cell is calculated by the photocurrent density measured at short-circuit (J_{sc}), the open-circuit photovoltage (V_{oc}), the fill factor of the cell (FF) and the

intensity of the incident light (P_{inc}) by the relation,

$$\eta = FF(V_{oc}J_{sc}/P_{inc})$$

$$FF = (I_{mp} \times V_{mp}) / (J_{sc} \times V_{oc})$$

where, I_{mp} is the maximum power point current, V_{mp} is the maximum point voltage.

Photovoltaic properties of DSSCs :

The complexes (1-6) were assembled into sensitized DSSCs devices to study the influence of the electron-donating group and coordination on the DSSCs performance was tested under irradiation of 100 mW cm^{-2} by ADCMT 6241 DC voltage/current source/

monitor. The data of J_{sc} , V_{oc} and FF for these devices are shown in Fig. 7 and presented in Table 7. The higher value of V_{oc} corresponds to higher harvest of the light energy. The efficiencies are found in the order $4 > 6 > 1 > 5 > 3 > 2$. Complex (4) and (6) show higher V_{oc} and J_{sc} , which indicates the higher efficiency as compared to the other complexes. The strongest light harvesting ability of the complex 6 is also supported by the appearance of band 2 in calculated electronic spectra. However, band 2 of 4 indicating the highest V_{oc} value is ascribed to electron transfer towards -COOH group.

Fig.7. The J-V plots for complexes 1-6.

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Table 7. The parameters of DSSC performance for **1-6**

Dye	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF	η (%)
N ₃	0.6803	6.0247	0.26	1.0824
Mn-nap	0.0861	0.0084	0.28	2.05×10^{-4}
Fe-nap	0.396	0.0050	0.26	0.52×10^{-4}
Co-nap	0.425	0.0103	0.26	1.15×10^{-4}
Ni-nap	0.1668	0.0305	0.29	1.48×10^{-4}
Cu-nap	0.0304	0.0264	0.22	1.75×10^{-4}
Zn-nap	0.0739	0.0660	0.26	1.26×10^{-4}

The metal order of efficiency is Ni > Zn > Mn > Cu > Co > Fe as listed in Table 6. Efficiencies of DSSC with **4** and **5** showed an order of magnitude larger value than other cells, this is due to comparatively higher V_{oc} and J_{sc} .

The enhanced J_{sc} values will be discussed in conjunction with the incident photon-to-current electron conversion efficiency (IPCE) spectra shown in Fig. 8 and the parameters are provided in Table 6 to know the degree of energy conversion from light harvesting toward electricity at each light wavelength. The complex (**4**) show the highest value (7%) around 350 nm corresponds to band 2 in calculated UV-Vis spectra. This transfer results in high value of IPCE. Complex **6** show the efficiency (η) next to **4** and also exhibit the high IPCE value too. It may be concluded that complexes **4** and **6** can be exploited as dyes in DSSC cells and increase the conversion efficiency of the cell.

Fig. 8. IPCE spectra for fabricated DSSC with complexes **1-6**.

Conclusion

The newly synthesized naphthyl-salen type mono-nuclear complexes of Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Zn have been characterized using elemental analysis and FT-IR. The structures are ascertained through X-ray diffraction on crystal analysis. The metal ions in all the complexes were pentacoordinate, square pyramidal geometry. The UV-Vis-NIR, TD-DFT calculation, magnetic properties were also measured and all the five complexes along with the Cu complex previously synthesized and characterized by us. Similar to previous systems²³, UV-Vis-NIR electronic spectra of these complexes were also measured and inference of electron transfer of each absorption band is estimated by TD-DFT calculations. The complexes (**1-6**) were assembled into sensitized DSSCs devices to study the influence of the electron-donating group and coordination in the DSSC. The Ni-nap and Zn-nap show comparatively stronger absorption, high V_{oc} , J_{sc} and show suitable HOMO-LUMO band of dye for electron cycle in cell as compared to other complexes. Thus, these two complexes may be exploited as dye in DSSC.

CCDC 1540627-1540631 contain the supplementary crystallographic data. These data can be obtained free of charge via <<http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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